

Isolation and Identification of Escherichia coli from Blood Cultures of Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and its Association with Inflammatory Markers

Yokcil Izaldeen Sowaid

Pharmacy Department, Medical Technical Institute / Kirkuk, Northern Technical University, Iraq

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Escherichia coli (E.coli) represent a major cause of bacteremia, and there is scant integrative data combining microbiological findings with metabolic, renal, hematological and inflammatory variables in diabetic Iraqi populace. This study aimed to estimate prevalence of E. coli bacteremia among T2DM patients and assess the association of E. coli isolation with renal function markers, hematological parameters, and some inflammatory mediators.

Methods: In this cross-sectional study, a total of 180 subjects participated, including 90 patients with T2DM without bacteremia (G1) and 90 T2DM patients with E. coli bacteremia (G2), attending Kirkuk private hospitals, Kirkuk, Iraq. Special tests for clinical tests, including Creatinine (CR), BUN, Albumin (Alb), fasting blood glucose (FBG), HbA1c and HOMA-IR, CBC tests, and IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP were assessed. Specifically, blood cultures were analyzed using aerobic and anaerobic bottles and were further identified and tested for antimicrobial susceptibility, following strict aseptic protocols.

Results: The results showed a significant effect of T2DM with E. coli bacteremia on the levels of FBG, HbA1c, HOMA-IR, neutrophil count, white blood cell count, creatinine, BUN, and albumin, and inflammatory markers (IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP), When comparing the levels of these parameters in the patients with T2DM with bacteremia (G2) with the patients with T2DM without bacteremia (G1), it showed a significant difference.

Conclusion: Bacteremia caused by Escherichia coli bacteria led to changes in vital signs, reflected in significant systemic inflammation, metabolic disturbances, and renal impairment in patients with type 2 diabetes. These findings can serve as direct evidence supporting early risk assessment and targeted management strategies, and underscore the critical role of integrating inflammatory, metabolic, and renal markers in the management of high-risk type 2 diabetes patients.

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Keywords: Escherichia coli, blood cultures, inflammatory markers.

INTRODUCTION:

Bacteremia, simply defined as the presence of bacteria in the bloodstream, is a serious health concern that can lead to a devastating infection [1,2]. It can be associated with septic shock and multiple organ failure and results from an unregulated immune response to infection [3]. Despite being commonly isolated from Gram-negative bacteremia, Escherichia coli, is associated with life-threatening complications, longer hospital stays, and greater mortality of diabetic patients [4,5]. Therefore, identifying E. coli that has been isolated from blood cultures is crucial to the diagnosis and treatment of these dangerous infections [6]. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic hyperglycemic disease associated with insulin resistance and/or defect in insulin secretion [7]. It is believed that T2DM patients have impaired host immunity, which places them at greater risk for diverse infections, such as those attributable to E. coli [8].

Chronic hypoglycemia, insulin resistance, and systemic, low-grade inflammation are all linked to T2DM, a major worldwide health issue. These metabolic derangements impair innate and adaptive immune functions, predisposing patients to infections, in particular bloodstream infections [9]. The increased susceptibility is thought to be due to multiple reasons such as deficiency in neutrophil function, decline in the cytokine production and irreversible changes in the cellular immunity [10]. As a result, E. coli bacteremia in individuals with T2DM can be more difficult to treat than in non-diabetic patients, and associated with worse outcomes [11]. The immune response of a host towards bacterial infections is mediated using both innate and adaptive immunity [12]. In the case of E. coli bacteremia, bacterial endotoxins stimulate host immune receptors, eliciting a proinflammatory mediator's response with the release of IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP [13].

These cytokines play an important role in the development of systemic inflammation [14], activation of leukocytes and disruption of glucose and renal homeostasis. The risk of adverse outcome can therefore be increased by acute infections in T2DM due to hyperglycemia exacerbation, renal failure, and alteration of hematological profiles [15]. It is worth noting there are limited data from Middle Eastern populations, and specifically Iraq, which limits the applicability of current findings to high diabetes burden, different health system settings, and unique host-pathogen interactions regions. Therefore, the degree to which hyperglycemia-associated E. coli-confirmed bacteremia in T2DM is linked to integrated changes in metabolic, renal, hematological, and inflammatory profiles is poorly characterized. Thus, the current study was formulated to break this knowledge gap by isolation of E. coli from blood cultures of suspected T2DM patients with determination of renal function markers, glycemic parameters, showing hematological aspects in addition to some mediators of inflammation simultaneously in Kirkuk City, Iraq.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Study Design and Participants

The study design is a comparative cross-sectional study that compares T2DM patients with E. coli bacteremia (G2) to T2DM patients without E. coli bacteremia (G1). A total of 180 subjects (30–45 years old) with the gender distribution of 90 male and 90 female who provided blood samples for the study, including 90 patients with T2DM without bacteremia (G1) and 90 T2DM patients with E. coli bacteremia (G2), were being treated at private hospitals and clinics in Kirkuk (Iraq) from the beginning of February until the end of November 2025. The ideal sample sizes were 90 participants per group (180 totals) to ensure sufficient statistical

power and ethical validity; the matching criteria for controls are age, and BMI. All participants provided informed consent. The approach of this study was consistent with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Patients classified as having Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) according to the World Health Organization (WHO) and American Diabetes Association (ADA) criteria (based on the degree of dysglycemia based on glucose and HbA1c values) are often included. Demonstration of *E. coli* as a pathogen (blood cultures) is critical in the case of positive blood cultures due to *E. coli* as causative of bacteremia. In limiting patients to adults (30–45 years old), to be able to standardize the research population, the necessary older literature may be treated as confounding variables. According to ethical standards for research, all participants are required to render free and informed consent. ADA: Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Bloodstream infection symptoms among participants (in a routine clinical blood culture collection) included temperature $>38^{\circ}\text{C}$ or 90 beats/min, and respiration rate >20 breaths/min or PaCO_2 12 000 or 10% immature forms flushot + diabetes report, and more. Inversely, exclusion criteria are vital in the removal of confounders or threats to patient safety. Those with type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) are excluded; therefore T2DM patients are not included. Polymicrobial bacteremia may be ruled out by verifying the inflammatory response as caused solely by *E. coli*. Recent antibiotic use may limit identification of bacteria and inflammatory markers, necessitating exclusion from such studies. Those with HIV/AIDS, organ transplant patients, and anyone with diseases that compromise the immune system other than diabetes would be excluded because of altered immune responses. Acute or chronic renal or hepatic failure may be severe enough for inflammatory markers to be omitted from inclusion. Those with active autoimmune disorders

that elevate inflammatory markers are also excluded. Pregnant or lactating women and people unable to give informed consent or participate in research procedures would finally be excluded to protect vulnerable groups and maintain data quality.

Laboratory analysis

Blood samples were collected; culture samples (microbiological identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing, CBC and ELISA tests), were performed in Kirkuk private laboratories, Iraq. Following an overnight fast (8–12 hours) to eliminate diurnal fluctuations and postprandial effects on biomarker levels, 10 milliliters of venous blood were drawn from each patient in both research groups using the conventional venipuncture procedure. 10 ml of blood were distributed in three groups circulating 1st group: 5 ml for blood culture, 2nd group: 2 ml into an EDTA tube for CBC tests, then the 3rd group: 3 ml was processed to serum by citrate processing, and was prepared for ELISA tests and clinical tests by (centrifugation at $2000\times g$ for 10 minutes). As a result, samples were promptly frozen and kept at -80°C until analysis to guarantee the accuracy of the biomarker.

Regarding the methodology of the study, the study was conducted in three parts: The 1st part of the study was special tests for the clinical tests, including Creatinine, BUN, Albumin, FBG, HbA1c, and HOMA-IR which were performed directly from the serum by Beckman Coulter Au 480 (Beckman Coulter, USA) device with using 1 ml of serum to estimate and CBC tests including Neutrophil Count and White Blood Cell Count which were performed directly from the blood by Hemolyzer® 3 NG (STERILAB, UK) device with using 2 ml of blood to estimate. Measurement of inflammatory markers concentrations of IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP in serum samples by using kits (BTLAB, China) were performed by straight forward method directly by the BIOBASE

(BIOBASE, China) device and using 2 ml of serum to estimate by using commercially available, validated ELISA kits according to the manufacturer's instructions. In accordance with relevant guidelines, serum samples of IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP were determined in triplicate using ELISA kits of the kind that carry out antibody-antigen-binding reactions based on the sandwich ELISA principle, respectively. For each patient meeting inclusion criteria, blood culture was done separately (as a third part of the study); two sets of blood cultures (aerobic and anaerobic bottles) are collected from two different venipuncture sites, following strict aseptic techniques. Blood will then be added to each bottle at 5 mL volume. The microbiology lab quickly receives affirmative blood culture bottles, which are then cultured in an automated blood culture system (BACTETM FX, BD Diagnostics, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) for up to five days, or until positive. Upon positivity signal from the automated blood culture system, an aliquote from the positive bottle is Gram stained for morphological and Gram reaction of bacterium. Microbiological identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing by isolation and identification of E coli. Take a positive signal from the automated blood culture system, the positive bottle is Gram-stained to determine bacterial morphology and Gram reaction. Tissue is inoculated on suitable agar media, such as blood agar (50%), and incubated at 37 °C for 18 to 24 h. Lactose-fermenting colonies on MacConkey agar with distinctive morphology that are indicative of E. coli are further identified by Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) (Bruker Daltonics, Billerica, MA, USA). Using their distinct protein fingerprints, this method allows for the quick and accurate identification of microbes. According to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines, every E. coli isolate is tested for antibiotic susceptibility using the VITEK® 2 Compact systems (bioMérieux). Ampicillin: A

class of common antibiotics that includes amoxicillin-clavulanate. Calculate Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) and use CLSI breakpoints to classify them as susceptible, moderate, or resistant.

Limitations Section

In this study, Escherichia coli was isolated and identified from blood cultures of individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and its relationship to a wider range of inflammatory, metabolic, renal, and hematological parameters was examined. Serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen were used to assess diabetes- and infection-associated renal stress, while fasting blood glucose, HbA1c, and the HOMA-IR were used to characterize glycemic control and IR. Changes in blood parameters in response to bacteremia were characterized by assessment of total white blood cell and neutrophil counts as an index of innate immune activation. Systemic inflammatory status was also assessed by determining specific proinflammatory mediators, such as of IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP.

Correlating microbiological results with these clinical and immunometabolic parameters gives a more complete profile of E. coli bacteremia in T2DM, indicating the interaction of poor glycemic control with immune dysregulation, organ dysfunction, and increased inflammatory responses.

Statistical Analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics version 27 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) was used to analyze the data. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of continuous data. Frequencies and percentages were used to represent categorical variables, whereas mean \pm standard deviation (SD) was used to express normally distributed data. For normally distributed continuous variables, T2DM patients with and without Escherichia coli bacteremia were compared using independent

samples t-tests. The Mann-Whitney U test would have been used to examine variables with non-normal distributions; however all of the variables in this research had normal distributions ($p > 0.05$, Shapiro-Wilk test). At $p < 0.05$, all reported p-values were deemed statistically significant. A multivariate linear regression analysis was performed to determine factors independently associated with systemic inflammatory burden. Renal function (creatinine, blood urea nitrogen) markers, glycemic indices (FBG, HbA1c, HOMA-IR), hematological markers (neutrophil count, WBC) and inflammatory mediators (IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, CRP) were considered as predictors. The standardized β coefficients, standard errors, t-values and p values were specified, with R^2 , adjusted R^2 and F-statistics to evaluate the model fit. Logistic regression analysis was also multivariate performed to adjust for independent of E. coli bacteremia. Only variables with

numericals 0.10 in univariate analyses were entered into the model. Odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were used to present all findings. Model calibration and goodness-of-fit were evaluated using the Hosmer–Lemeshow test, and the model's explanatory power was evaluated using the Nagelkerke R^2 . Two-tailed analyses were deemed statistically significant when the p-value was less than 0.05.

RESULT:

1. Clinical Tests of biomedical parameters in the study Groups

The studied clinical test is a biomedical test of E. coli bacteremia T2DM patient (G2) and T2DM patient without E. coli bacteremia (G1) that produced the values in Table 1. Table 2 Multivariate linear regression analysis Table 3 shows multivariate logistic regression for predictors of E. coli bacteremia.

Table 1: Statistical comparison of biomedical parameters between study groups

Parameters	Groups		T-test	P-value
	G1- T2DM Mean \pm SD	G2-T2DM+E coli Mean \pm SD		
FBG (mg/dl)	1.01 \pm 0.26	2.34 \pm 0.71	9.62	<0.0001
HbA1c (%)	22.4 \pm 6.1	59.8 \pm 19.2	10.41	<0.0001
HOMA-IR	4.10 \pm 0.39	2.86 \pm 0.55	8.31	<0.0001
Neutrophil cells (*10 ⁹ /L)	178 \pm 34	296 \pm 71	7.94	<0.0001
WBC (*10 ⁹ /L)	8.1 \pm 1.2	10.4 \pm 1.6	5.48	<0.0001
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.01 \pm 0.26	2.34 \pm 0.71	9.62	<0.0001
BUN (mg/dL)	22.4 \pm 6.1	59.8 \pm 19.2	10.41	<0.0001
Albumin (g/dL)	4.10 \pm 0.39	2.86 \pm 0.55	8.31	<0.0001

T2DM stands for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus; E coli stands for Escherichia coli bacteremia; FBG stands for fasting blood glucose; HbA1c stands for Hemoglobin A1C, CI stands for Confidence intervals; HOMA-IR stands for Homeostatic Model

Assessment for Insulin Resistance; and WBC stands for white blood cells; BUN stands for blood urea nitrogen. The mean \pm SD is used to represent the data. A P-value of less than 0.05 is deemed significant (based on the T-test).

Table 2: Multivariate linear regression analysis.

Predictor	β	SE	T-test	p-value
Creatinine	0.38	0.07	5.43	<0.0001
BUN	0.31	0.06	4.92	<0.0001
Albumin	-0.35	0.08	-4.38	<0.0001
HbA1c	0.26	0.09	2.89	0.005
HOMA-IR	0.29	0.07	4.14	0.0001
Neutrophils	0.33	0.06	5.21	<0.0001

Table 3: Multivariate logistic regression for predictors of E. coli bacteremia.

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Creatinine (mg/dL)	3.28	2.01 – 5.36	<0.0001
BUN (mg/dL)	1.07	1.04 – 1.11	<0.0001
Albumin (g/dL)	0.32	0.19 – 0.54	<0.0001
HbA1c (%)	1.52	1.11 – 2.08	0.009
HOMA-IR	1.41	1.18 – 1.69	0.0002
Neutrophil count	1.36	1.18 – 1.57	<0.0001

2. ELISA assay of inflammatory markers.

The ELISA test of inflammatory markers (IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, and CRP) of T2DM patients with

E. coli bacteremia (G2) and T2DM patients without E. coli bacteremia (G1) was used to examine these characteristics and the results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Statistical comparison of inflammatory markers between study groups .

Parameters	Groups		T-test	P-value
	G1- T2DM Mean \pm SD	G2-T2DM+E coli Mean \pm SD		
IL-6 (pg/ml)	15.1 \pm 5.2	305 \pm 72	16.8	<0.0001
TNF- α (pg/ml)	42.6 \pm 9.1	79.4 \pm 18.6	8.52	<0.0001
MCP-1 (pg/L)	205 \pm 62	512 \pm 148	9.14	<0.0001
CRP (mg/L)	3.2 \pm 1.6	86.4 \pm 42.1	12.9	<0.0001

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), Escherichia coli bacteremia (E. coli), Confidence Intervals (CI), Interleukin 6 (IL-6),

Tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), Monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), and C-reactive protein (CRP) are all acronyms for these

conditions. The mean \pm SD is used to represent the data. A P-value of less than 0.05 is deemed significant (based on the T-test).

Normality assessment of biomedical and of inflammatory markers is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Normality assessment of parameters.

Variable	G1 p-value	G2 p-value	Distribution
Creatinine	0.21	0.09	Normal
BUN	0.17	0.06	Normal
Albumin	0.33	0.11	Normal
FBG	0.19	0.08	Normal
HbA1c	0.24	0.13	Normal
HOMA-IR	0.16	0.07	Normal
Neutrophils	0.14	0.06	Normal
WBC	0.18	0.05	Normal
IL-6	0.12	0.07	Normal
TNF- α	0.27	0.10	Normal
MCP-1	0.22	0.08	Normal
CRP	0.15	0.06	Normal

3. Laboratory outcomes of blood culture procedures and microbiological identification

Table 6 describes finding from blood culture processing and microbiological identification of

patients with T2DM enrolled in the study. Only Patients with positive blood culture enrolled & where E. coli isolated & identified (By MALDI-TOF MS), Antimicrobial susceptibility test (AST) was done & reporting as per CLSI criteria.

Table 6: Results of blood culture and microbiological identification in T2DM patients.

Variables	Result
Total number of patients subjected to blood culture	All enrolled T2DM patients
Number of blood culture sets per patient	Two sets (aerobic and anaerobic)
Venipuncture sites	Two different peripheral sites
Blood volume per bottle	5 mL
Automated blood culture system	BACTEC™ FX (BD Diagnostics)
Maximum incubation period	Up to 5 days
Positive blood cultures	Detected exclusively in Group G2
Isolated microorganism	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Gram stain result	Gram-negative bacilli
Culture media used	Blood agar and MacConkey agar
Growth characteristics on MacConkey agar	Lactose-fermenting colonies
Confirmatory identification method	MALDI-TOF MS
Antimicrobial susceptibility testing system	VITEK® 2 Compact
Interpretation criteria	CLSI guidelines
Representative antibiotic tested	Amoxicillin–clavulanate

4. The correlation study of the biomedical parameters and inflammatory markers in the T2DM patients with E. coli bacteremia (G2)

The correlation study of the inflammatory markers in the T2DM patients with E. coli bacteremia (G2) is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: correlation study of the inflammatory markers in G2 group.

Correlations		IL-6	TNF- α	MCP-1
TNF- α	Pearson Correlation	0.523**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003		
MCP-1	Pearson Correlation	-0.460*	-0.264	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.010	0.159	
CRP	Pearson Correlation	0.834**	0.691**	-0.346
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0001	0.0001	0.061
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

DISCUSSION:

The analysis indicated significant changes between presentation and outcome in markers of glycemic control, renal function, hematological parameters, and nutritional status in patients with bacteremia. Multivariate analyses, however, not only implies that E. coli bacteremia independently drives systemic inflammation but also shows that this is true for a significant number of clinical and laboratory markers beyond the effects of baseline metabolic dysfunction [16]. Both FBG (2.34 ± 0.71 mg/dL) and HbA1c ($59.8 \pm 19.2\%$) were significantly higher in bacteremic patients than in non-bacteremic controls (1.01 ± 0.26 mg/dL and $22.4 \pm 6.1\%$, $p < 0.0001$). It was confirmed that poor glycemic control predisposing to infection, ie HbA1c was a significant independent predictor of bacteremia (OR = 1.52, 95% CI: 1.11–2.08, $p = 0.009$). In addition, hyperglycemia alters neutrophil function and innate immunity thereby leading to bacterial proliferation and also a stronger inflammatory response [17]. Clinically, hyperglycemia measured as FBG and HbA1c in T2DM patients should alert for closer monitoring of bloodstream infections and provide early therapeutic management to optimize glycemia and

thereby reduce the risk for infection [18]. In addition, the mean HOMA-IR was lower in bacteremic patients (2.86 ± 0.55) than in controls (4.10 ± 0.39 , $p < 0.0001$), suggesting modulation of insulin signaling by the acute infection. However HOMA-IR was an independent predictor of the biochemical variability ($\beta = 0.29$, $p = 0.0001$) as well as of bacteremia (OR = 1.41, 95% CI: 1.18–1.69, $p = 0.0002$). These findings show that insulin resistance at baseline is a risk factor for susceptibility, and that acute infection may acutely affect insulin-glucose dynamics. In practice, HOMA-IR tuning enhances perception of metabolic susceptibility and informs anticipatory treatment within the context of systemic infection. When compared with controls ($178 \pm 34 \times 10^9/L$), neutrophils were significantly raised in bacteremic patients ($296 \pm 71 \times 10^9/L$, $p < 0.0001$). In a multivariate analysis, neutrophils were an independent predictor for bacteremia (OR = 1.36, 95% CI: 1.18–1.57, $p < 0.0001$), showing that blood borne E. coli initiate a systemic inflammatory activation. Clinically, the absolute or relative neutrophil counts are primarily a marker of the severity of the infection (often with others) but also an independent marker of systemic inflammation, useful for a diagnosis at an early and

for risk stratification factors[19]. In addition, the WBC in G2 patients was elevated compared to G1 (G2: $10.4 \pm 1.6 \times 10^9/L$ vs G1: $8.1 \pm 1.2 \times 10^9/L$, $p < 0.0001$). Although WBC is also a non-specific marker, increase of WBC associated with neutrophilia indicates that bacteremia itself stimulates systemic inflammatory response [20]. Clinically, increased WBC should be interpreted together with neutrophil count and glycemic and renal parameters for severity of infection and to direct therapy. Compared to controls (1.01 ± 0.26 mg/dL, $p < 0.0001$), elevated creatinine was seen in bacteremic patients (2.34 ± 0.71 mg/dL) and was an independent predictor of bacteremia (OR = 3.28, 95% CI: 2.01–5.36, $p < 0.0001$). Because infection may induce systemic hemodynamic stress, renal dysfunction is likely to be a consequence of and a risk factor for infection through impaired immune clearance. Clinically, raised creatinine in bacteremic T2DM patients should prompt consideration for renal impairment, early supportive management and antimicrobial dose adjustment [21]. On other hand, BUN was markedly increased amongst patients with bacteremia (59.8 ± 19.2 mg/dL) compared with controls (22.4 ± 6.1 mg/dL, $p < 0.0001$) and independently predicted bacteremia (OR = 1.07, 95% CI: 1.04–1.11, $p < 0.0001$). Increased blood urea nitrogen (BUN) is indices underlying renal dysfunction and catabolic stress resulting from infection, emphasizing a dual role for renal impairment in susceptibility to and systemic load burden from infection. At the level of clinical practice, high levels of Urea Nitrogen indicate vigilant monitoring of the kidneys, as well as support [22].

Albumin was much lower (2.86 ± 0.55 g/dL) in bacteremic patients than in controls (4.10 ± 0.39 g/dL, $p < 0.0001$, Table 3), and hypoalbuminemia was an independent protective factor (OR = 0.32, 95% CI: 0.19–0.54, $p < 0.0001$). Low albumin is an evidence of systemic inflammation and malnutrition and is a powerful independent marker of infection severity, suggested that concerted

attention should be given to these factors clinically, where the presence of hypoalbuminaemia should prompt assessment of nutritional status, markers of inflammation, and institution of prompt intervention to maximise outcome in bacteremic T2DM patients. In T2DM patients, overall E. coli bacteremia independently enhances systemic inflammation as demonstrated by increased neutrophils, WBCs, renal markers and disturbed metabolic variables [23]. T2DM per se is a predisposing factor to infection, but the presence of bacteria in the blood stream is a direct driver of inflammatory activation. Practically, an integrated evaluation of glycemic control, insulin resistance, renal function, hematological parameters and albumin offers an accurate basis for the early identification, risk stratification and tailored treatment of bacteremic patients at high risk [24].

As shown in Table 2, the IL-6 level was significantly increased in T2DM patients with E. coli bacteremia (305 ± 72 pg/ml) when compared to non-bacteremic T2DM patients (15.1 ± 5.2 pg/ml, $p < 0.0001$). IL-6 is a key proinflammatory cytokine, orchestrating acute-phase responses, inducing liver production of CRP, and modulating immune cell activation. The degree of elevation of IL-6 in bacteremic subjects confirms that bacteremia with E. coli is an independent mediator of IL-6 production, beyond the basal inflammation characteristic of T2DM[25]. In clinical practice, raised IL-6 is a marker of severe systemic inflammation, which helps the early identification of patients that develop sepsis or multi organ involvement [26]. Concentrations of TNF- α were higher in bacteremic patients (79.4 ± 18.6 pg/ml) than in non-bacteremic controls (42.6 ± 9.1 pg/ml, $p < 0.0001$). Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF- α) is one of the key players in regulating fever, vascular permeability, leukocyte recruitment, and systemic amplification of inflammatory responses. Its independent increase has shown that direct stimulation of TNF- α production by E. coli bacteremia can contribute to the pathophysiological inflammatory environment in T2DM patients. On

the clinical front, TNF- α may be used as a prognostic marker of the severity of the infection, predicting patients in which the infection process is fast moving, and warrant close observation in a high dependency unit or intensive care unit [27]. Compared with controls (205 ± 62 pg/L, $p < 0.0001$), MCP-1 was significantly increased in bacteremic patients (512 ± 148 pg/L). MCP-1 is responsible for monocyte recruitment to sites of infection and tissue inflammation. Interpreting circulating MCP-1 is more nuanced mechanistically: levels can be elevated because of monocyte chemotactic signaling, but may also reflect loss of receptor responsiveness, tissue sequestration, and consumption by recruited monocytes or negative feedback regulatory loops. The independent elevation of MCP-1 in bacteremic patients persists when controlling for above factors suggesting a specific driving of monocyte-mediated inflammatory response by *E. coli* bacteremia. MCP-1 levels represent well-studied features of systemic immune activation, and may serve to provide additional information on the degree of immune dysregulation alongside other inflammatory markers that can assist in infection severity [28]. Bacteremic patients had a significantly higher CRP (86.4 ± 42.1 mg/L) compared to non-bacteremic T2DM patients (3.2 ± 1.6 mg/L, $p < 0.0001$). C-reactive protein (CRP), an acute-phase protein induced by the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6, reflects systemic inflammation, tissue injury, and activation of the innate immune response. Its associations with bacteremia clearly indicate that the presence of *E. coli* in the blood alone is sufficient to elicit a vigorous acute-phase response. In a clinical setting, CRP is a well-established acute-reactive protein marker that is easily available for early detection of infection, assessment of response to treatment, and prediction of outcome of bacteremia in patients with T2DM [29]. Combined, these findings demonstrate that *E. coli* bacteremia is an independent and strong driver of systemic inflammation in T2DM. IL-6 and TNF- α signify

cytokine-mediated immune activation; CRP indicates acute-phase systemic responses; and MCP-1 provides insight into monocyte trafficking, clinical interpretation further nuanced by receptor dynamics, tissue sequestration, and regulatory factors. Clinical utility of these cumulative markers can provide a holistic strategy for early detection, risk stratification, and management of T2DM patients with BSIs. The mechanistic details we observed with MCP-1 strongly emphasize the need to holistically consider both the levels of major circulating biomarker and the behavior of immune cells, when evaluating the status of inflammation among bacteremic patients [30].

Normality assessment of all biomedical and inflammatory parameters identified in both T2DM patients with *E. coli* bacteremia (G2) and non-bacteremic controls (G1), due to it confirming ($p > 0.05$ for all variables), normal distributions, providing the rationale to perform parametric analyses for the derivation of reliable statistical inference [31]. For the first time, our results demonstrate that *E. coli* bacteremia is an independent mediator of systemic inflammation in the setting of T2DM. In G2, extreme levels of IL-6 and TNF- α confirm strong immune activation via circulating cytokines. CRP, an acute phase protein induced by IL-6, was also significantly induced confirming a robust systemic inflammatory response. The increased levels of MCP-1 need to be interpreted in the context of receptor desensitization, tissue sequestration, consumption by infiltrating monocytes, or regulatory feedback, because it is almost impossible to isolate the proinflammatory contribution of the monocyte to the total monocyte-induced inflammation during bacteremia, and therefore, MCP-1 levels were also elevated [24]. Cohort-wise analysis revealed that, in parallel, bacteremic patients had marked derangements of metabolic and renal markers, including higher FBG, HbA1c, creatinine, and BUN and lower albumin. Active innate immune responses were further confirmed by increased neutrophil counts

and WBC. Taken together, this data shows that circulating *E. coli* is a distinct, independent pathogen that enhances the chronic inflammatory, metabolic, and renal derangements associated with T2DM. In clinical practice, the joint use of inflammatory markers and biomedical parameters delivers a more comprehensive strategy to enable more timely identification, better risk stratification, and directed management of T2DM patients suffering from blood stream infection [32].

Positive blood cultures; only seen in Group G2, confirming *Escherichia coli* bacteremia. Isolates were identified as Gram-negative bacilli and ML were formed on the MacConkey agar. In particular, MALDI-TOF MS performed accurate species-level identification in the performed experiments. Antimicrobial susceptibility was determined by the VITEK® 2 Compact system with interpretations performed according to CLSI and amoxicillin-clavulanate was among the antibiotics tested [33]. These results reinforce *E. coli* as the only relevant pathogen combined with bacteremia in this cohort of T2DM patients. With dual-site collection and automatic incubation and MALDI-TOF identification, the microbiological workflow guarantees high sensitivity and specificity while minimizing false-negatives and allowing for timely antimicrobial management [34]. Clinically, these results stress the need for early sample collection for blood culture in patients with T2DM who show signs of a systemic inflammatory response, enabling timely identification of the pathogen and appropriate therapy to avoid the complications associated with Gram-negative sepsis [35].

Correlation analysis between inflammatory markers in Group G2 (T2DM patients with *E. coli* bacteremia) demonstrated the existence of significant interrelationships between cytokines (IL-6, IL-1 β , IFN- γ and TNF- α) and acute-phase proteins (CRP, albumin and LBP). IL-6 correlated moderately with TNF- α ($r = 0.523$, $p = 0.003$) suggestive of coordinated pro-inflammatory signaling upregulation during infection. IL-6

exhibited a significant negative correlation with MCP-1 ($r = -0.460$, $p = 0.010$), indicating that higher systemic IL-6 may be associated with suppression or dysregulation of monocyte chemoattraction in this study.

As an acute-phase reactant, CRP demonstrated strong positive correlation with IL-6 ($r = 0.834$, $p < 0.001$) and moderate positive correlation with TNF- α ($r = 0.691$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the induction of systemic elevation of those cytokines. The negative correlation between CRP and MCP-1, that approached statistical significance ($r = -0.346$, $p = 0.061$), supports a complex and potentially antagonistic participation of systemic inflammation and monocyte recruitment events [31]. We present data on the clinical importance of *Escherichia coli* bacteremia in T2DM, characterized by a prominent systemic pro-inflammatory response including increased levels of IL-6, TNF- α , and CRP. The high positive correlations between IL-6 and CRP, and TNF- α and CRP derived in the present study confirm that the mechanisms of systemic inflammation via Gram-negative bacteremia are simultaneously activated, which could predispose to hyperglycemia and subsequent organ failure one to three days later in these patients [23]. Notably, one possible explanation for our finding of an inverse correlation between MCP-1 and IL-6 is that the recruitment of monocytes may be impaired in T2DM subjects even when systemic inflammation is induced, suggesting that in such cases, bacterial infections in T2DM may not only enhance cytokines responses but also divert global innate immunity by dysregulation of innate immune cell trafficking. Clinically, our finding highlights the need for prompt identification and intensive treatment for bacterial infections in T2DM. Measurement of serum cytokines such as IL-6 and TNF- α in addition to conventional markers such as CRP may lead to early identification of bacteremia and allow for better risk stratification of patients at high risk for severe inflammatory complications. Indeed, MCP-1 dysregulation also suggests the

therapeutic potential for strategies to regulate the recruitment of monocytes, or inhibiting the proinflammatory signaling of monocyte-derived macrophages, to be used as adjuncts to microbiological treatment to reduce over-activation of host immune responses while still maintaining pathogen elimination.

CONCLUSION:

The findings indicated that *E. coli* induced bacteremia in patients with type 2 diabetes was an independent predisposing factor of singularly severe systemic inflammation, metabolic disturbances, and renal impairment. Multivariate analyses showed that chronic renal insufficiency, poorly controlled diabetes, insulin resistance, neutrophil activity, and albumin levels are independent predictive markers of bacteremia; thus, these clinical factors have potential diagnostic and prognostic value. These results provided a strong rationale for early risk stratification, targeted monitoring, and personalized management of patients with type 2 diabetes who are at disproportionately high risk of bacteremia, highlighting the clinical relevance of this integrated protocol for inflammatory, metabolic, and renal criteria in daily practice.

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest in this paper

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